

ENHANCING EAP READING AND VOCABULARY ACQUISITION THROUGH CONSTRUCTIVIST DRAMA ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. English for Academic Purposes (EAP) classes in many high schools are often ineffective due to lack of collaborative reading activities, limited focus on vocabulary, and low student motivation. These challenges result in weak reading comprehension and disengaged learners. The aim of this paper is to examine how **constructivist learning combined with drama activities** can improve students' participation, reading comprehension, and vocabulary acquisition in EAP classes. Constructivist approaches provide autonomy and shared ownership of knowledge, while drama encourages interaction, creativity, and project-based learning. Drama-based strategies also support vocabulary development. By linking new words to prior knowledge, incorporating physical movement, and engaging in dramatized activities, students can retain vocabulary more effectively and find learning more meaningful. It is concluded that integrating constructivist principles with drama can transform passive reading lessons into dynamic, collaborative, and motivating experiences. This approach offers EAP teachers a practical method to enhance both comprehension and vocabulary development.

Keywords: English for Academic Purposes (EAP), constructivist learning, drama activities, collaborative learning, vocabulary acquisition, motivation, project-based learning.

KONSTRUKTIVIZMGA ASOSLANGAN DRAMA FAOLIYATLARI ORQALI EAP DARSLARIDA O'QISH VA LUG'AT O'ZLASHTIRISHNI YAXSHILASH

Annotatsiya. Ko'plab maktablarda English for Academic Purposes (EAP) darslari samarali emas, chunki ularda hamkorlikka asoslangan o'qish faoliyatlari yo'q, lug'at o'rganishga yetarlicha e'tibor berilmaydi va o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi past bo'ladi. Bu muammolar natijasida o'qish tushunishi sustlashadi va talabalar darsdan ajralib qoladilar. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi – **konstruktivistik yondashuv va drama faoliyatlarini birlashtirish** orqali o'quvchilarning ishtiroki, o'qish tushunishi va lug'at o'zlashtirishini yaxshilashni o'rganishdir. Konstruktivizm o'quvchiga mustaqillik va bilimni birgalikda egallash imkonini beradi, drama esa interaktivlik, ijodkorlik va loyihaga asoslangan ta'limni rag'batlantiradi. Drama asosidagi strategiyalar, shuningdek, lug'atni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Yangi so'zlarni oldingi bilimlarga bog'lash, jismoniy harakatlarni qo'shish va dramatik mashg'ulotlardan foydalanish orqali talabalar so'zlarni samaraliroq eslab qoladilar va ularni mazmunliroq o'zlashtiradilar. Xulosa qilib aytganda, konstruktivizm va dramani birlashtirish orqali passiv o'qish darslarini dinamik, hamkorlikka asoslangan va motivatsion tajribaga aylantirish mumkin. Bu yondashuv EAP o'qituvchilari uchun o'qish tushunishi va lug'atni rivojlantirishda samarali usuldir.

Kalit so'zlar: EAP, konstruktivistik yondashuv, drama faoliyatlari, hamkorlikda o'qish, lug'at o'zlashtirish, o'qish tushunishi.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ПОНИМАНИЯ ЧТЕНИЯ И УСВОЕНИЯ СЛОВАРНОГО ЗАПАСА НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ EAP С ПОМОЩЬЮ КОНСТРУКТИВИСТСКИХ ДРАМАТИЧЕСКИХ АКТИВНОСТЕЙ

Аннотация. Во многих школах занятия по English for Academic Purposes (EAP) оказываются малоэффективными из-за отсутствия совместных видов чтения, ограниченного внимания к изучению словарного запаса и низкой мотивации учащихся. Эти проблемы приводят к слабому пониманию прочитанного и снижению вовлеченности студентов. Цель данной работы – изучить, как **конструктивистское обучение в сочетании с драматическими активностями** может повысить участие учащихся, их понимание текста и овладение словарным запасом на уроках EAP. Конструктивизм предоставляет студентам автономию и совместное владение знаниями, тогда как драма стимулирует взаимодействие, креативность и обучение на основе проектов. Драматические стратегии также способствуют развитию словарного запаса. Связывая новые слова с предыдущими знаниями, включая физическую активность и инсценированные задания, учащиеся лучше запоминают лексику и усваивают её более осмысленно. Таким образом, интеграция конструктивизма и драматических активностей способна преобразовать пассивные уроки чтения в динамичные, совместные и мотивирующие. Этот подход представляет для преподавателей EAP практический метод повышения как понимания текста, так и словарного запаса.

Ключевые слова: EAP, конструктивистское обучение, драматические активности, совместное обучение, усвоение словаря, понимание прочитанного.

Introduction. English for Academic Purposes (EAP) classes play an essential role in preparing high school students for academic studies. However, in many schools, EAP reading lessons are often ineffective because of several challenges. These include a lack of collaborative learning activities, limited attention to vocabulary acquisition, and low student motivation. As a result, learners often struggle with reading comprehension and feel bored and demotivated during reading lessons. Previous studies (Yang, 2022) also point out that students' achievement in EFL reading is negatively affected by poor engagement, lack of reading strategies, and uninteresting class activities. Therefore, it is crucial to find innovative approaches to make EAP reading classes more engaging, collaborative, and effective.

The aim of this paper is to explore how **constructivist learning integrated with drama-based activities** can improve reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition in EAP classes. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. Encourage student motivation and active participation in reading classes through drama activities.
2. Promote collaborative learning and project-based approaches in EAP classrooms.
3. Enhance vocabulary retention and comprehension by linking new words to prior knowledge and using physical movement in drama-based learning.

Main Discussion

At our high school in English for Academic Class, we have faced many difficulties. Our high school don't provide a language collaborative learning activities in reading and teachers do not care about vocabulary acquisition in EAP classes. As a result , students can not motivated to

take part reading classes and feel boring to learn new vocabulary as well. This leads to low reading comprehension and non-effective EAP class. Constructivist learning which cooperates with drama activities is essential for those who learn English as a second language. We will explain problems and how we can make Constructivist activities work.

Xinyuan Yang (2022) points out that students' achievement in EFL reading classes is negatively affected by three main challenges: a lack of engagement in classroom activities, struggles in comprehending reading texts, and limited familiarity with effective reading strategies. Students face problems related to reading and reading classes due to unstimulating reading class and unfamiliarity with reading strategies, because reading lessons make students boring and demotivated to participate in reading lessons, we want to encourage teachers to implement constructivism based drama activities and to create collaborative learning environment. Firstly, in drama-oriented classes, learners are more incentivized to learn and participate in reading lessons because they can enjoy autonomy which means to control over their knowledge. According to Spencer (2019) drama-oriented EFL reading classes greatly benefit from the inclusion of autonomy and shared ownership of knowledge as essential elements. Secondly, Constructivism enables students to interact with each other and gain knowledge in real life situations which is important in their communication skill. Lastly, Drama-integrated EFL reading activities call for students to simulate particular situations, usually in groups, based on each student's unique interpretation of the contents of reading materials. Yang (2022). This will promote project based learning among students.

According to Shiela R & Alber and Carolyn R. Foil (2003) students who have limited vocabulary development often encounter challenges in acquiring crucial language arts skills, such as reading comprehension. EAP teachers do not pay attention to vocabulary acquisition in reading class. To tackle this problem, we have some ideas. First, students have difficulty in vocabulary learning, we want to encourage teachers to implement drama activities focused on teaching vocabulary. Secondly, some students can not remember new words and forget them easily. To fix this, we want to encourage teachers to connect to learners' prior knowledge and give time to discussion to find a connection. The extent to which students are able to link new vocabulary words to prior knowledge influences their levels of comprehension. Shiela R & Alber and Carolyn R. Foil (2003). Lastly, to enhance vocabulary development, we will recommend to use drama activities incorporating with physical movement to practise vocabulary definitions. This will make students feel special about certain words as a result they can remember them easily.

By doing these things, we want to help students to take part in reading lessons actively and to learn vocabulary effectively in EAP classes. I believe constructivism based drama activities is the key to active learning and making reading class more stimulating which can attract students' attention and promote collaborative learning. These are beneficial in school EAP classes.

Conclusion

The integration of constructivism and drama into EAP reading lessons can significantly improve students' motivation, vocabulary acquisition, and comprehension skills. By transforming passive reading lessons into interactive and project-based experiences, this approach creates a collaborative learning environment where students take an active role. Ultimately, constructivist drama activities make EAP instruction more engaging, effective, and beneficial for both teachers and learners in high school settings.

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